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Role: President

Entity: The Friends of L. Ron Hubbard Foundation

Session 3: Minorities representation in the Media

Thank you Madame Chair,

Esteemed members and delegates,

I am a Scientologist and represent, in Italy, the legacy of an advocate for human rights, L. Ron Hubbard, a writer, a humanist and the founder of the religion of Scientology. His actions inspire me today in this forum in which I wholeheartedly participate.

I want to start my statement with the recommendation: adopting policies that encourage journalists' continuous training on Minority Issue to generate content that authentically represents the diverse cultures of minorities.

I wish to draw your attention to the situation of religious minorities in Italy, it involves 2.3 million people, 5% of the entire population. Here are some key numbers:

- 1.5 million Muslim people;
- more than 800 minority religious groups;
- based on the data given by government agency called Unar, in 2023, we have the shame of 3 discrimination reports per day.

And what about media representation? In Italy minorities are poorly represented in the media, due, to some degree, to the functional illiteracy which has poisoned also Journalism. For a concrete example, we see the use of non-neutral terms that carry negative connotations, discriminating and perpetuating prejudices or stereotypes, such as the term “cult”, often used in headlines and articles, directed to some minorities. We, as scholars or advocates for religious Minorities, know that the word “cult” is been abandoned by the scientific community, and it has been replaced, decades ago, with neutral words.

Madame President, this is the RECOMMENDATIONS. We recommend adopting policies that encourage journalists' continuous training on Minority Issue to generate content that authentically represents the diverse cultures of minorities. Thank you.

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